

**PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTIVE
AND INTEGRATED METHODS IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES**

Xorazm viloyati Xonqa tumani

10-sonli maktabi ingliz tili fan o`qituvchilari

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Annotation: In the article, the researcher discusses the results of research on the importance, operation and effectiveness of new pedagogical methods in teaching English, especially interactive and integrated methods. Most of the methods as a sample are analyzed in depth and form.

Keywords: method, interactivity, student, foreign languages, importance, curricula, reading load.

Аннотация: В статье исследователь рассматривает результаты исследования важности, практики и эффективности новых педагогических методов, особенно интерактивных и интегрированных, в обучении английскому языку. Форма и содержание большинства методов выборки тщательно анализируются.

Ключевые слова: метод, интерактивность, студент, иностранные языки, образовательные программы, учебная нагрузка.

As one of the means of knowing and communicating with the surrounding world, a foreign language occupies a special place in the modern education system due to its social, cognitive and developmental functions. Taking into account that the position of the English language as a leading tool of international communication in the world is growing stronger and there are no serious trends to stop or slow down this process, the problem of using effective methods in this regard is being posed. English teaching is very important. In the modern sense, the educational process is considered as a process of interaction between the teacher and students to introduce students to certain knowledge, skills, abilities and values. Each teaching method organically includes the educational work of the teacher (presentation, explanation of new material) and the organization of active learning and cognitive activities of students. That is, the teacher, on the one hand, explains the educational material himself, on the other hand, he tries to stimulate the learning and cognitive activity of students (encourages them to think, make independent conclusions, etc.).

A foreign language lesson is considered as a social phenomenon, where the class is a certain social environment where the teacher and students enter into certain social relations with each other, the learning process is an interaction of all participants. At the same time, success in learning is the result of collective use of all opportunities for learning. And students have to contribute a lot to this process. In all classifications there are methods of verbal presentation of knowledge. These include story, explanation, explanation, conversation, briefing. Verbal methods are used at all stages of learning: during preparation for mastering new material, during its explanation, assimilation, generalization and application. A story is a figurative, colorful, lively monologic presentation of educational material by the

teacher. This method is often used in lower classes. When it is necessary to inform children about bright, new facts, events, things that children cannot directly observe, the teacher turns to the story. The story is a powerful source of influence on the mental activity, imagination, and emotions of young students, and expands their worldview. If the story has more signs of a passive method, explanation is an active method of coherent, logical, clear presentation of complex issues open to children. Explanation, of course, is combined with children's participation, their own observations, experiments and demonstration of movement patterns, illustrations.

The explanation is supplemented with instructions for performing operations, actions, tasks: how to learn a poem, do an exercise, organize a workplace, etc. Narrative, explanation and lecture are monologue or informative teaching methods.

Conversation is a dialogic method of presenting educational material (from the Greek Dialogos - a conversation between two or more persons), which in itself speaks about the important characteristics of this method. The essence of the conversation is that the teacher, through skillfully asked questions, encourages students to think, to activate thinking, to analyze the facts and events being studied in a certain logical sequence, to independently approach relevant theoretical conclusions and generalizations.

"Round discussion" method is very important in mastering the English language. It is known that in the method, the teacher formulates a problem and offers students a task. The student can evaluate the importance of the problem in the process. Students will be able to talk about the issue presented. They discuss their positions and come to a common decision. One well-known method is Brainstorming, which

focuses on problem solving rather than discussing it. However, according to this method of teaching English, the audience is divided into two groups - "idea generators" who actually propose ideas, and "experts" who evaluate the position of each at the end of the "attack". It is known that the effectiveness of the game method in teaching foreign languages will be positive, considering that the English language teachers we train teach elementary or high school students. The main advantages of the game method are the absence of a mechanism of forcing lessons, and the child's great interest is formed precisely in the game. The teacher conducts various games with the children on the learned vocabulary and grammatical structures, in which the children quickly memorize them and learn to use them in speech. In addition, the audio-lingual method of teaching English is also very important. The essence of this method is the child's understanding of foreign speech by ear. A characteristic feature in this case is the method of analogy used in memorizing new words. In doing so, we can teach the reader basic language constructions and frequently used vocabulary. This method, in turn, makes it easier to construct sentences and connections on everyday topics. This method is also distinguished by the ability to memorize various dialogues. First, it is the development of basic grammatical and lexical structures using a basic set of words. Then gradually the dictionary is filled with new lexical units. If we talk about games in the classroom, then they serve as a kind of break and help to shift attention from one task to another. Consequently, concentration and, of course, mood increases. Games are used at any stage of the lesson, whether it is the development of phonetic rules, grammatical or lexical topics, the development of reading rules, as well as listening practice. Role-playing games help to activate thinking, arouse interest in a certain type of activity, to perform a certain exercise,

and are also the most powerful motivational factor that satisfies schoolchildren's need for novelty of the studied material. The use of role-playing games provides ample opportunities to enhance the educational process. The game gives timid, insecure students the opportunity to speak up and thereby overcome the barrier of uncertainty. In a typical discussion, the student leaders take the lead and the shy students stay silent. A role-playing game is a conditional reproduction of the real practical activities of people by its participants, creating conditions for real communication. Here, the effectiveness of training is primarily related to the explosion of motivation, increased interest in science.

Alexander, an English pedagogue, identified patterns or features in English that clearly distinguish it from Russian. And he built his methodology on the basis of the study of these patterns and emphasized that a foreign language can be understood only by studying its differences from the local language.

Characteristics of English according to Dragunkin's approach: English has inflected and inflected words. In the second grade there are 27 lexical units, which are "central figures" in learning. The author invents his own schemes that allow him to put all his incomprehensible things on "shelves". He also found a unique way of explaining the use of tenses in English.

The following criteria should be followed when applying the selected methods in English.

- Your level of readiness;
- how much time you can devote to lessons;
- Financial opportunities;

- Dose preferences and desires.

Also, information can be received more easily in the following ways: by ear, through a textbook, using video lessons, in a playful way, etc. The student's interests are also taken into account. His own opinion, personal interests should not be neglected. In order to help the student as much as possible, it is necessary to explain the channel of his perception and, accordingly, the direction of tasks.

A conversation is a dialogue: the teacher's questions and the students' answers. The student's mind follows the teacher's mind, as a result of which the students move step by step in acquiring new knowledge. According to the appointment, interviews are divided into:

- 1) introductory or organizational;
- 2) communication of new knowledge;
- 3) synthesize or identify;
- 4) control and correction. According to the level of cognitive independence of students, reproductive and heuristic conversations are distinguished.

An introductory (preparatory) interview is usually held before the start of training. Its purpose is to determine whether students have correctly understood the meaning of the upcoming work, and have a good idea of what and how to do it. Interview (explanation) can be: question-and-answer, avoiding objections, memorizing answers; Socratic (gentle, respected by the student, but allowing doubts and objections); heuristic (putting the student in front of problems and demanding his own answers to the questions posed by the teacher). All types of conversation are

used in elementary school. Synthesizing (final or strengthening) conversations serve to summarize and systematize the knowledge available to schoolchildren, and control-corrective (checking) conversations are used for diagnostic purposes, as well as for the development, clarification, and completion of new facts or rules. is used when knowledge that students have. In order to conduct the interview successfully, the teacher must seriously prepare for it. It is necessary to clearly define the topic of the interview, its purpose, create a plan-concept, choose visual aids, form the main and auxiliary questions that may arise during the interview, and think about the methodology of its organization and conduct. Allow students to argue in pairs. Students must defend the opposing side of their personal opinion. It encourages them to step away from their beliefs and occasionally teaches them to look through a different colored glass. Below we will analyze some of the interactive methods for learning English.

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